
COVID-19 LOCKDOWN AND FAMILY STABILITY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

COVID -19 pandemic poses a serious threat to the well-being of families due to the challenges of financial insecurity, care-giving burden and confinement related stress which will have a long standing consequences on the family system. This research is therefore, set to examine COVID-19 pandemic and its possible influence on family stability in Nigeria. The study used secondary sources of data and the cross-sectional research design. Findings from the study reveal that family life has been influenced by COVID-19 pandemic through the implementation of physical and social distancing, quarantine, and staying at home to curb the spread of the coronavirus. The study recommends, among others, that families should stay connected with communication, managing conflict and making quality time within family, they should promote family resilience through shared beliefs and close relationships within families; the readiness and knowledge of healthcare providers and counselors should be improved upon to provide counseling services to help families who have physical and mental health problems; Non-governmental organizations should increase public awareness to staying connected and reporting any family violence; government should take action to mitigate the social,

economic, and health impacts of the pandemic on families, especially those who are vulnerable to losing household income.

Keywords: Family, Stability, Instability, Covid-19 Lockdown, Well-being

Introduction

Overtime, there have been different forms of diseases that had threatened human existence. According to Martin & Howard (2009), the Spanish flu, which hit the USA between 1918 -1920, is estimated to have killed over 40 million. During this time, companies implemented non-medical practices aimed at preventing the spread of the infection, many industries asked their staff to stay at home, while few were selected for administrative purposes and special duties.

In October 2019, the world witnessed a pandemic called COVID-19, which surfaced in the city of Wuhan in China (Nick & Do, 2020). As at September 2020, COVID-19 cases have crossed in excess of 31 million coupled with the loss of lives higher than 900,000 (World Health Organization, 2021). Apart from the human effect, there is also a huge monetary and history of massive health, social and economic devastation on the world leading to its declaration as a global health pandemic in early 2020 by the World Health Organization (Sampson et al., 2020; International Monetary Fund, 2020). According to National Center for Disease Control (2020) and Jugu & Obaka (2020), Nigeria recorded the first COVID-19 index case on February 27, 2020 with an Italian national; and as at September 23, 2020, the population reached 57,613, while the number of discharged cases was 48,836 with 1,100 deaths representing 1.9% fatality rate.

Nigeria was among the first countries in Sub-Saharan Africa to identify COVID-19 cases and has since implemented strict measures to contain the spread of the infection (Jugu & Obaka, 2020). The adverse effects of the COVID-19 pandemic remains largely unprecedented as thousands of lives were lost on a daily basis across the globe and workers were not only downsized but relieved from their jobs. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic and its subsequent label as a global pandemic significantly altered life, including employment, with many businesses/organizations temporarily or permanently closing, and workers shifting to remote/virtual working

environments (Halel, 2020). National Bureau of Economic Research (2020) noted that between February and May 2020, over 30% of the United States' labor force transitioned to working from home (WFH), and 10% of workers were laid off. These significant alterations to employment status and working environment transformed behaviors of workers. While some individuals who worked from home (WFH) found increased time and opportunities to engage in other activities due to reduced commuting time, others significantly increased sedentary time, particularly screen-based time (Straker, 2020). Interestingly, the alteration in the mode of work leading to the Work from Home (WFH) model meant that even the family domain had to witness some form of adjustment and readjustments.

Consequently, the family is a primary social unit and the oldest institution on earth, and gives legitimacy to sexual relationship and reproduction of legitimate children (Udom, Nnabuk & Umanah, 2020). The stability of a family is threatened when there is any factor that is alien to such stability which would definitely amount to family instability.

Family instability refers to changes in parents' residential and romantic partnerships such as marriage, divorce, and romantic partners moving in or out of the home (Sydney, 2019). As rates of cohabitation, non-marital births, and divorce have increased over the past 60 years, more children have experienced some degree of family instability. Furthermore, increase in family instability can have a negative influence on both parents, the children and adolescents' functioning and behavior (Sydney, 2019). Not all families have been equally affected by the increase in family instability. Families in which the parents are not married and have low household income are much more likely to experience family instability than families with married parents and higher household income. Family instability influences adults' functioning as do household income and parents' relationship status. Family stability can promote positive social behaviors in children and adolescents, while instability is associated with social maladjustment, including behaviors such as aggression toward peers, teachers, or parents.

Family instability is any factor that creates additional challenges within a family unit that ultimately affects a child/children's cognitive, behavioral and emotional development, and places their development at significant risk due to

the parents' inability to effectively manage the home and the living environment. Family instability can come in many forms - economic, emotional, social, and physical. The challenges and struggles of family instability can be passed on from generation to generation if the instabilities are not corrected or the family and children do not receive appropriate physical and emotional assistance when needed (Coach, 2019). There are many factors responsible for instability of family - poverty, lack of attention, among others, could affect family stability. Hitchings & Maclean (2020) noted that the COVID-19 health crisis strongly undermined the mental health of a good number of the human population; the pandemic may have produced psychological distress and collateral concerns for parents during a greater part of the lockdown due to unstable financial circumstances, school closures, and suspended educational services for children. It is against this background that this study sets out to investigate how COVID-19 lockdown contributed to family stability in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Family stability is the continual existence of family without divorce or separation. A stable family can be unstable where there are issues combating the stability of the family. Family instability has hindered the growth and progress of many marriages, homes and even children and many factors could be responsible for this disappointing situation. It is clearly established that through marriage, families are established and family is the fundamental unit of human society (Esere, Yusuf & Omotosho, 2011). Marriage gives legitimacy to sexual relationship and reproduction for legitimate children (Omoniyi-Oyafunke, Falola & Salau 2014) and it is linked to significant benefits in the area of physical and mental health. These benefits stem from economic advantages associated with married status.

Moreover, most marriages have challenges but how each challenge is handled is what matters. Some partners do not have the mental capacity or mental strength to handle some problems or situations that come along with being married as one recent study has shown that at the end of the day 4, 10 out of every married couple end up either in separation or they end up getting divorce (Grain, 2019). Corroborating this, Coach (2019) has shown that this is even more problematic during periods of global distress either as a result of health pandemics or economic failures.

In Nigeria, the government announced a total lockdown to contain the spread of the virus. The lockdown included a ban on all non-essential travels as well as the closure of the majority of non-essential businesses and instructing workforces to work from home. Where working at home was not possible due to technological and financial constraints, companies either issued redundancies or furloughed staff under the government Job Retention Scheme. It was estimated that over 8 million jobs were furloughed globally, during which time the government paid up to 80% of the median salary (Bell & Jane, 2020). Being furloughed by an employer is associated with poorer mental health, with higher levels of stress and anxiety recorded (Qualtrics, 2020). COVID-19 pandemic did not only have public health consequences but also severe economic impacts that imposed some adverse effects on the family/marital institutions (Udom, Ukommi & Udom, 2023). Although the long term impacts of COVID-19 pandemic on families are yet to be fully understood, families around the world are struggling to keep up with the changing demands and constraints of the pandemic (Andrade et al., 2022). Alternative employment options and work arrangements including the shift to working from home, work overloads, and technological challenges contribute to family tension (Chung et. al., 2020).

Several studies have been conducted on the impact of COVID-19 on households across the world. For instance, Briggs & Kattey (2020) in a study of mental and social health-related complaints among children and adolescents in Nigeria found that some children without internet services experienced boredom, while others were anxious, sad and stressed out. A study by Portu (2020), which examined the effect of the COVID-19 lockdown on parents, found strong negative outcomes in terms of the mental health of the general population. Findings point to the fact that COVID-19 enabled psychological distress and collateral concerns for parents in lockdown as a result of unstable financial circumstances, social exclusion arising from the social distance measure, school closures, and suspended educational services for children. A subsequent study by Kalil, Mayer & Shah (2020) examined the associations between economic hardship, exposure to the virus, and pandemic-induced increases in childcare time on parental mental health and stress, parent-child interaction, and children's adjustment. They found both positive and negative effects of the pandemic on households. On the negatives, they reported that parental job and income losses are strongly associated with parents' depressive symptoms, stress, diminished sense of hope, and negative interactions with children. However, on the positive side, they found that parents who lose jobs but do not experience concomitant income losses are associated with more

positive parent-child interactions. Furthermore, parents' exposure to COVID-19 is associated with less positive parent-child interactions and more child behavior problems; while in contrast, parents who reported spending substantially more time in childcare as a consequence of the pandemic had more positive parent-child interaction.

It is worthy of note that bulk of these studies on COVID-19 tried to look at the socioeconomic impact of the pandemic on small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) and general healthcare of the people without any research or literature on its influence on family stability. This is the gap this research hopes to fill.

Review of Related Literature and Theoretical Framework

Conceptual review

Impact of Covid-19 on the family

This current article draws from pertinent literature across topic areas of acute crises and long-term, cumulative risk to illustrate the multitude of ways in which the well-being of children and families may be at risk during COVID-19. According to Prime, Wade & Browne (2020), the COVID-19 pandemic poses an acute threat to the well-being of children and families due to challenges related to social disruption such as financial insecurity, care-giving burden, and confinement-related stress which includes crowding, changes to structure, and routine. The consequences of these difficulties are likely to be longstanding, in part because of the ways in which contextual risk permeates the structures and processes of family systems.

Impact of COVID-19 on Psychological and Mental Disorder

Mental health is a state of well-being whereby an individual is able to adjust to normal stresses of life, recognizes his/her abilities and be productive in his/her daily activities. Covid-19 disrupted social connections between people and their social activities, many have reported feeling depressed and lonely during the pandemic. According to Drake (2021) the number of people who are depressed, anxious and feeling lonely increased during the lockdown. Cullen, Gulati & Kelly (2020) added that the presence of Covid-19 has increased loneliness which has invariably increased the level of depression and suicidal motive. Also, it is worthy of note that an outbreak of an infectious disease has a psychological effect on the individual, causing emotional distress and social disorder during and after the lockdown.

Furthermore, the psychological consequences of COVID-19 pandemic are enormous as report from the Mental Health America (MHA) reviewed that those who thought about suicide or self-harm have speedily increased beyond the usual level (Drake, 2020). This means that mental health has drastically increased and will likely continue after the pandemic.

Covid-19 lockdown caused mental trauma in children and adolescents; it has profound negative impact on children's well-being due to its unprecedented changes in lifestyle as it created a hindrance on physical activities and increased in domestic violence. According to Briggs & Kattey (2020), the Covid-19 pandemic has affected the mental and social well-being of Nigerian children. Despite these, some studies have shown a high rate of stress and other mental conditions in parents.

COVID-19 has caused an up-end in the health care system, thereby limiting individuals from accessing services and resources to ameliorate the conditions. The disruption that occurred in the healthcare system as a result of Covid-19 lockdown hindered patients with chronic illnesses from accessing the facilities (Semo & Frissa, 2020). Specifically, the lockdown measures reduced social interactions and triggered several other psychological disorders (Olaseni, Akinsola, Agberotimi & Oguntayo, 2020); likewise the means of containment such as self-isolation, quarantine, social distancing caused further trauma on individuals infected by the disease and on family members.

In Nigeria for example, previous studies have shown that Nigerians experienced depression, insomnia and post-traumatic stress symptoms during the Covid-19 pandemic (Agberotimi et al., 2020). The unprecedented event caused by corona virus pandemic has caused an upsurge in mental health globally.

Covid-19 Pandemic and Education

Education is a guideline used to determine a country that is developed and that which is developing. Education is essential for any nation that wants to develop. With the outbreak of Covid-19, education in Nigeria and most developing nation has worsened. In Nigeria, in a bid to cushion the spread of Covid-19, the federal ministry of education on March 19, 2020, approved the closure of all schools as a response to the threat posed by the pandemic

(Amorighoye, 2020). In the same vein, the World Bank (2020) observed that, as of April 8, 2020, Universities and other educational institutions closed in 175 countries and communities, and over 220 million post-secondary students (-13% of the total number of students affected globally) have had their studies ended or significantly disrupted due to Covid-19. This closure of schools affected the primary, secondary and tertiary institutions within the country.

Furthermore, the Nigerian Education in Emergencies Working Group (2020) observed that over 46 million students within the country will be affected and also over 40,000 Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) children will be affected by stoppage of learning in schools. The disruption caused by Covid-19 on education led to online classes and distance education in which other countries that were unprepared struggled to meet up with international standard. This caused a setback in the academic calendar and in learning.

Covid-19 Pandemic and Health Sector

In Nigeria, the health sector is one of the worst hit sectors by Covid-19. Nigeria with other low-income countries (mostly in Africa) is quite vulnerable to the contagious spread of the deadly infections disease due to the poor economic system and weak health system (Moore, 2020). Corroborating this, Uzosike et al., (2020) stressed that the rapidly increasing number of cases and limited capacity of the health system is affecting positive patient outcomes and reducing the confidence and brevity of front-line health workers who are faced with the danger of becoming infected and being a source of spread of the disease. Undoubtedly, health workers play an important role in the combat against the spread of the deadly disease in Nigeria and thereby, suffer a greater risk of getting infected with the disease, likewise, undergo psychological trauma as front-line workers (Uzosike et al, 2020).

Unfortunately, Covid-19 pandemic poses a threat to health systems globally and community health workers contribute to the health system by increasing social mobilization, thereby filling in the gaps left in case of any future outbreak of disease (Boyce & Katz, 2019). In addition, the Covid-19 pandemic brought emergency funding and other complicated health challenges to the health sectors with an increase in mortality rate (Ihekweazu & Agogo, 2020).

During the lockdown, people became afraid to visit the hospital to avoid the risk of being infected with the disease. According to Ihekweazu & Agogo

(2020), the Honourable Minister of health stated that the latest Statistics from the National Health Management Information System indicates that outpatient visits dropped from 4 million to 2 million, antenatal visits from 1.3 million to 655,000, stillbirth attendants from 158,000 to less than 99,000, while immunization has dropped to about half. The Covid-19 pandemic has thrown the health sector off-balance, mounting pressure on health workers who are left with no option but to work with poor medical facilities and limited personnel in order to curb the menace caused by Covid-19.

Furthermore, on the 8th of April 2020, 22,073 confirmed cases of Covid-19 were recorded from 52 countries among health workers (International Labour Organization, 2020) and this alone can create a huge gap between health workers and their zeal towards fighting the pandemic. Despite its numerous negative experiences, Covid-19 created solidarity, consciousness and an improvement in hygiene through hand washing, environmental sanitation, enlightenment and precaution or an out watch on the symptoms of Covid-19 and generally created an awareness in case of future emergencies.

COVID-19 Pandemic Sexual and Domestic Violence

Sexual and domestic violence is a global issue that occurs on daily basis in both developed and developing countries of the world. Sexual violence also known as rape affects both physical and mental health of the victim. Domestic violence also causes physical and psychological trauma. Sexual and domestic violence on children is seen as child abuse according to child abuse Act 2003. This sexual and domestic violence against children and adults are acts of human right violation with harsh penalty unleashed on perpetrators (Abdullateef, 2020).

According to World Health Organization (2020), sexual violence is a sexual act, attempt to obtain a sexual act, unwanted sexual comments or advances, or acts to traffic, or otherwise directed against a person's sexuality using coercion by any person regardless of their relationship to the victim, in any setting, including but not limited to home and work. The world is struggling with the devastating effect of Covid-19, while Nigeria is faced with the challenges of rape and sexual violence against the girl child and women (Abdullateef, 2020). COVID-19 pandemic triggered a lot of violence, especially sexual and domestic violence during the lockdown which led to death of few and injury to many.

According to the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (2017), six out of every 10 children experience some form of violence and one in four girls, and 10% of boys have been victims of sexual violence. In addition to this, Nigeria has the largest number of child brides in Africa with more than 23 million girls and women married as children (Udom, Nnabuk & Umana, 2020).

A case of rape during the lockdown of a 22 years old Uwaila, Vera Omozuwa, Microbiology student at the University of Benin, who was raped and killed at the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Edo State, got many talking against the unacceptable act (Vanguard, 2020). Another similar case is that of Barakat Bello, an 18-year-old student of Science Laboratory Technology at the Federal College of Animal Health and Production in Ibadan, Oyo State, who was gang raped and killed by her rapist. Rape is not only common in Nigeria, but a social problem which occurs on a daily basis in different locations, and requires a strict social action from individuals and those in authority.

Sexual and domestic violence during the lockdown became outrageous which led many to the street for protest against the devaluing act orchestrated by perpetrators of rape. It is a serious public health problem which affects the physical and mental health of victims, leading to depression, sexually transmitted disease like HIV/AIDS, and sometimes suicide. According to the United Nations (2020), Africa and other developing countries should be on alert on the alarming rate of rape and domestic violence triggered by the coronavirus lockdown. Corroborating this, from January to June, 2020, Liberia's Minister for gender, children, and social protection received reports of more than 1,000 cases of sexual or gender-based violence; and this made President Weah to declare rape and all forms of sexual and gender-based violence as a National Emergency (Drachman, 2020). Rape and sexual violence are attacks on the body and dignity of a woman, such assaults have profound psychological, medical, economic, and social consequences for the rest of her life that plague survivors and their families (Sifat, 2020).

However, The United Nations Population Fund (2020) predicted a 20% increase in domestic and sexual violence during the Covid-19 lockdown. Related to this is a report conducted during the pandemic on rape and domestic violence from January to September 2020 in Bangladesh. The report revealed

that 397 women died as a result of domestic and sexual violence, only 208 cases were filed, 975 women were raped, 204 became victims of rape, 43 died after being raped, 12 women committed suicide after rape, and 762 women were raped by an individual while 208 suffered gang-rape (Kendra, 2020).

Furthermore, to examine the impact of Covid-19 on rape and domestic violence, Tandon (2020) and Khan (2020) reported cases of domestic abuse and violence since the lockdown. These cases have surpassed the actual number, making sexual and domestic violence a national issue that demands a spontaneous regulatory action to curb the challenge.

Family Perspectives of COVID-19

According to Shiley et al. (2020), the COVID-19 pandemic has uniquely affected children and families by disrupting routines, changing relationships and roles, and altering usual child care, school and recreational activities. Understanding the way families experience these changes from parents' perspectives may help to guide research on the effects of COVID-19 among children. As a multidisciplinary team of child health researchers, we assembled a group of nine parents to identify concerns, raise questions, and voice perspectives to inform COVID-19 research for children and families. Parents provided a range of insightful perspectives, ideas for research questions, and reflections on their experiences during the pandemic. Including parents as partners in early stages of COVID-19 research helped determine priorities, led to more feasible data collection methods, and hopefully has improved the relevance, applicability and value of research findings to parents and children.

Family Vulnerability and Disruption during the COVID-19 Pandemic

A study by Scaini, Caputi & Giani (2021) two risk pathways that may account for increases in child internalizing and externalizing problems during the COVID-19 pandemic are: one pathway operating through pre-existing family vulnerability and a second pathway operating through disruption in family functioning occurring in response to the pandemic. We assessed family disruption and family functioning with measures of key family-level and parenting dimensions, including family cohesion, conflict and routines, and parents' harsh discipline, lax discipline and warmth. In all models, pre-pandemic parent emotional distress, financial strain and child maladjustment

were included as co-variables. Analyses were conducted in a model-building fashion. First, computing structural equation models for each family and parenting dimension separately, then advancing significant dimensions into one integrated model for the family-level factors; and a second model for parenting quality factors. Results provided more support for the family disruption hypothesis across all tests.

Consequently, in the family-level domain, decreases in family cohesion and increases in family conflict each uniquely predicted subsequent child maladjustment. In the parenting domain, increases in harsh discipline and lax discipline each uniquely predicted subsequent child maladjustment. Family routines and parental warmth were not associated with child adjustment. However, parents' emotional distress prior to the pandemic exhibited a robust association with children's internalizing problems. These findings indicate that efforts to support families in adapting to unique conditions of the pandemic will yield the greatest effect for child adjustment.

Specifically, interventions should include efforts to help families maintain cohesion and manage conflict, and help parents minimize increases in harsh and lax discipline.

Theoretical framework

Functionalist theory

This study adopts the functionalist theory of Herbert Spencer (1903) as its theoretical paradigm. The functionalist theory explains how societies maintained the stability and internal cohesion necessary to ensure their continued existence over time. In the functionalist theory, societies are thought to function like organisms, with various social institutions working together like organs to maintain and reproduce them. The various parts of society are assumed to work together naturally and automatically to maintain overall social equilibrium, because social institutions are functionally integrated to form a stable system, and a change in one institution will precipitate a change in other institutions. On the other hand, dysfunctional institutions which do not contribute to the overall maintenance of a society, will cease to exist.

A common analogy popularized by functionalist theorist, presents these parts of society as "organs" that work toward the proper functioning of the "body" as a whole. In the most basic terms, it simply emphasizes "the effort to impute, as

rigorously as possible, to each feature, custom, or practice, its effect on the functioning of a supposedly stable, cohesive system". Consequently, "structural-functionalism" came to describe a particular stage in the methodological development of social science, rather than a specific school of thought (Ritzer & Stepnisky, 2014).

This approach looks at society through a macro-level orientation, which is a broad focus on the social structures that shape society as a whole, and believes that society has evolved like organisms. This approach looks at both social structure and social functions. Functionalism addresses society as a whole in terms of the function of its constituent elements; namely norms, customs, traditions, and institutions (Turner, Jonathan & Jan, 2005).

In relating the above theoretical assumptions to the present study, functionalist theory or functionalism views society as an organism that has structures or institutions that must work together for the well-being of the entire society. The proponents of this theory have argued that societies are thought to function like organisms, with various social institutions working together like organs to maintain and reproduce. The functionalists believe institutions come about and persist because they play a function in society, promoting stability and integration.

However, the COVID-19 pandemic ought to be a health issue that should primarily affect the health sector in society. But for the fact that what affects one sector of the society affects others, every other institution was affected by the pandemic. World economy was affected, politics was affected, social gathering was affected, education was affected, religion and the family institution was affected, and so many other areas of human survival and endeavor was affected by a single pandemic that attacked the health institution of the society. The diverse effects of COVID-19 pandemic on all other institutions of the society have justified the theoretical assumptions of the functionalist theory.

Conclusion

COVID-19 pandemic has put families in uncertain conditions without clarity on how long the pandemic will last. The pandemic has caused many challenges that impact on family unit and its functions, including distraction in family relationships. Family life has been influenced through the implementation of

physical and social distancing, quarantine, and stay-at-home in a bit to curb the spread of the coronavirus during the outbreak.

However, distancing requires adaptation among family members to improve family well-being. Sheltering results in a more frequent interaction among family members, but limits the opportunity to have a leisure time in the outside world. This condition, on the one hand, can create a quality time and intimate interactions among family members, but on the other hand, it may lead to long-standing high conflicts, occasional domestic violence and if not checked, may lead to divorce. In this condition, a home can be described as a place of warmth, love and safety or as a place of intimidation, abuse, and fear.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Families should stay connected with communication, managing conflict, and making quality time for every member.
- ii. Government should take action to mitigate the social, economic, and health impacts of the pandemic on families, especially those who are vulnerable to losing household income.
- iii. Non-governmental organizations should increase public awareness to staying connected and reporting any family violence.
- iv. The readiness and knowledge of healthcare providers and counselors should be improved upon to provide counseling services to help families who have physical and mental health problems.
- v. Government interventions are needed to improve maternal and child health and nutrition activities such as strengthening of food supply chain, reducing food insecurity, building a net social security program, and a cash support for the disadvantaged families during the COVID-19 pandemic.

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